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ANALYSIS OF THEORETICAL APPROACHES ON PAIRS OF WORDS IN LINGUISTICS

ANNOTATION: In this article, the theoretical views on pairs of words in linguistics are thoroughly researched. Pairs of words appear not only in our daily life, but also in fiction. Pairs of words always attract the reader's attention regardless of space and time. A compound word is a component word represented by a single hyphen. Pairs of words are found in every language, and we use them in most of our daily lives.

KEY WORDS: pairs of words, lexeme, semantics, word formation, lexical meaning, hyphen, development, source, content, anatomical relations, hyponymic relations, paronymy, synonymy relations.

АННОТАЦИЯ: В статье подробно исследуются теоретические взгляды на пары слов в языкознании. Пары слов часто встречаются не только в нашей повседневной жизни, но и в литературе. Пары слов всегда привлекают внимание читателя независимо от пространства и времени. Составное слово — составное слово, представленное одним дефисом. Пары слов есть в каждом языке, и мы используем их в большей части нашей повседневной жизни.

ОСНОВНЫЕ СЛОВА: пары слов, лексема, семантика, словообразование, лексическое значение, дефис, форма, источник, содержание, анатомические отношения, отношения гипонимии, партонимия, отношения синонимии.

This article is devoted to the analysis of theoretical views on pairs of words in linguistics. The fact that pairs of words are not only used in our daily speech, but also in fiction, clearly shows that the pairs of words acquire special relevance in the language. As noted by the linguist Muller, "Pairs of words attract the reader's attention no matter where and in what context they are expressed."¹

Pairs of words, which form a separate group according to the linguistic nature of the language and have a unique position in the system of word groups, are one of the topics that cause various debates among linguists of the world. A pair of words is defined in linguistics as follows, "two-component words expressing the same lexical meaning, written with a hyphen."²

As the following sources on double words in world linguistics, Agricola's "Worter und Wendungen", Brandsch's "Phraseologische Wendungen in der deutschen Sprache", Donalies' "Basiswissen Deutsche Phraseologie", Wolfgang Fleischer's "Phraseologie der deutschen Gegenwartssprache", Iskos A., Lenkova A.'s "Lesestoffe zur deutschen Lexikologie", Khojiev A. _ " Uzbek in the language kushma , couple and repeated suzlar " and Indian and Russian linguists VPBeskrovniy, K.Guru, ZMDimshist, OGUltsiferov, VIGoryunov, VVVinogradov, MIZadorojniy, at the same time, scientists such as EVFedorchik and GSLebedov, a representative of the Russian Orientalist school of the late 19th and early 20th centuries, We can see the theoretical research of pairs of words by KAKossavics and others in their scientific work.

¹Yedlichko M. I., Rubinstein, Deutsche Redensarten. Phraseological expressions in the German language. Moscow. Uchpedgiz, 1953, p. 3.

²"Uzbekistan National Encyclopedia" State Scientific Publishing House Tashkent. p. 115

It can be observed that in this scientific study, the scientific and theoretical views specific to the pair of words were studied, and different opinions of scientists were given regarding the pair of words.

Pairs of words are words formed by joining two words together. Pairs of words exist in any language, and in some ways contribute significantly to the richness of that language. Many scholars have different interpretations of the formation of double words. For example, the German linguist Agricola says: "Pairs of words always consist of two (in some cases three) similar words. They are closely related words ³, Uzbek linguist A. According to Hajiyev, "a pair of words is a word that is formed on the basis of the equal connection of two parts that do not have a lexical meaning, and expresses such meanings as generalization, totality; the double form of the word, the pause (pause) between the two parts of the word is short; means happiness, brothers, day and night, long and short . ⁴Another one of our leading linguists, Ganiyev.FA, gives the following definition to double words: "Double words belong to the second method of formation of new lexical units (formation of words). Double words "In the formation of words, the syntagmatic relationship of the parts is carried out with the help of an equal relationship. This feature serves to distinguish them from adverbs-compound words, whose syntagmatic relationship of their parts is characterized by a subordinate relationship."⁵ A number of lexical-content (lexical-semantic) relationships between the parts of a pair of words also apply. They include: 1) the relationship of hyponymy (hand-foot, melon-watermelon, goat-capricorn, apple-apricot and hokozo); 2) the relation of synonymy (strength, fire, desire, desire, love, crooked, single, smart, alert, slowly, etc.); 3) relation of antonymy (young-old, boy-girl, white-black, good-bad, hot-soap, went-came, etc.); 4) partonomy relationship (moon-sun, mountain-stone, etc.). Pairs of words also belong to the grammatical (syntactic) process of joining words. The components of a pair of words also express a logically equal object-phenomenon relationship.⁶ Pairs of words are called "Wortpaare" in German. "They are formed by pairing words that are close and opposite in meaning."⁷ For example, bei Wasser und Brot- bread-water, in Wehr und Waffen-weapon-weapon, mit Strumpf und Stiel-tag with vein, kurz und gut-short.⁸

At the same time, there are pairs of words in the German language that are close to each other, but also words that have opposite meanings. For example, mit Recht und Unrecht-right and wrong, in Lust und Leid-lie-love, gross und klein-big-small, Rede und Antwort stehen-point-to-point.

It is worth noting that in Hindi, the pair of words "जोड़ी शब्द -joRi shabd" . Below we see a pair of Hindi words that are close in meaning to each other:

आदान-प्रदान - weapons

अगड़म-बगड़म - lies

आना-जाना -coming and going

कच्चे-बच्चे -child

³Klappenbach R.Stemitz W.Wterbuchder deutschen Gegenwartssprache.Bd.6.Berlin,Akademie,1982,S.4395.

⁴Hojiyev.A. Isohli lug'ati of Tilshunoslik terms. State scientific nashriyoti , 2002-40- b .

⁵G'aniyev __ F. _ A. _ Suffixal word-former in modern Tatar literary language. -Kazan, 1974.-S.4.

⁶Berdialiev A., Mashrabov A. Conjunction and disjunction relations in lexical meanings (in the example of some words expressing kinship)// Language and literature teaching, 2001; 4-c; Hetmonova A.D. Logic.- M: Higher school 1986.

⁷Imyaminova Sh , Tilovova G. _ German _ and it 's Uzbek in their languages couple words __ dictionary " . _

⁸Imyaminova Sh, Tilovova G. "Dictionary of pairs of words in German and Uzbek languages".

कहा-सुना - to say, examples of pairs of words that are semantically opposite to each other, we can cite the following,

आगर-मगर -if -but

अगल-बगल - 1) around , 2) on both sides

अफरा-तफरी - 1) up and down, commotion

आमद-खर्च - input-output (expenditure)

उत्तर-पूख -shim al-east⁹

In this case, double words are formed with the sign "hyphen" (-) in Uzbek, while in German, double words are formed with the conjunctions "und,oder", and in Russian, in some cases, "и"(and) and sometimes with a "hyphen" (-).

In conclusion, it can be said that each language has its own special place for pairs of words. A pair of words is a combination of words that are close and opposite in meaning.

In world linguistics, many opinions and opinions of linguists regarding double words were studied and researched.

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⁹Hindi-Russian dictionary. Compiled by A.S. Barkhudarov, V.M. Veskrovny, G.A. Zograf, V.M. Liperovsky. Edited by V.M. Beskrovny. T|-||.-M.: Soviet Encyclopedia, 1972.